

ASYMPTOTIC DQ SOLUTIONS OF LAMINATED CIRCULAR CONICAL SHELLS

Chih-Ping Wu¹ and Yu-Chang Hung²

^{1,2} *Department of Civil Engineering, National Cheng Kung University, Tainan, Taiwan 70101, Republic of China*

SUMMARY: The asymptotic differential quadrature (DQ) solutions for the bending analysis of laminated circular conical shells are presented. The formulation begins with the basic equations of three-dimensional elasticity. By means of proper nondimensionalization and asymptotic expansion, the three-dimensional equations can be decomposed into recursive sets of differential equations at various levels. After successive integration, we obtain the recursive sets of governing equations of a laminated circular conical shell. The DQ method is adopted for solving the problems of various orders. The differential operators corresponding to the governing equations of various orders remain the same, and the nonhomogeneous terms of the higher-order problems are related to the lower-order solutions. Thus, solution procedure of the DQ method for the leading order can be repeatedly applied for the solution to the higher-order level. The illustrative examples are given to demonstrate the performance of the theory.

KEYWORDS: Conical shells, the differential quadrature (DQ) method, the classical shell theory, bending analysis, asymptotic theory, perturbation, Fourier series expansion, transverse stresses.

INTRODUCTION

The literature on the three-dimensional solutions of laminated circular conical shells is scarce. Recently, several analytical solutions for the free vibration and buckling problems of laminated circular conical shells were presented [1]–[2]. On the basis of the classical shell theory (CST), their solutions are obtained using the power series method. In their formulations the stiffness coefficients are simply treated as the constants to make the power series method feasible. For a three-dimensional formulation the stiffness coefficients of a laminated conical shell should be functions of the longitudinal coordinate, since the scale factors are dependent on the longitudinal coordinate. This fact involves the mathematical complexities in the

formulation for the analysis of laminated circular conical shells. Hence, the use of the existing analytical approach is restricted.

An efficient numerical method, called the differential quadrature (DQ) method [3]–[4], was proposed for the solution of linear and nonlinear partial differential equations. The merit of the DQ method is to approximate a spatial derivative of an unknown function at a particular grid point as a weighted linear sum of the functional values at all the grid points in the whole domain. The DQ method was successfully employed in various structural problems [5]–[6]. The application of the DQ method in computational mechanics was reviewed by Bert and Malik [7]. In view of the efficiency and accuracy of the DQ method, it becomes an appropriate numerical method for the analysis of laminated circular conical shells.

An asymptotic theory for the bending analysis of laminated circular conical shells is presented in this paper. The asymptotic theory finally turns out recursive sets of governing equations with variable coefficients and coordinate-dependent stiffness coefficients. The DQ method is used to determine the asymptotic solution of the laminated circular conical shell in a consistent and hierarchic manner.

THEORY

Consider a laminated circular conical shell as shown in Fig.1, in which $2h$ denotes the thickness of the shell. A set of the orthogonal curvilinear coordinates (s, θ, ζ) is located on the middle surface. R_1 and R_2 are the radii of the cone at the small and large edges, respectively. α is the semivertex angle of the cone and L is cone length along the generator.

The stress-strain relations for the monoclinic material are given by

$$(1) \quad \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_s \\ \sigma_\theta \\ \sigma_\zeta \\ \tau_{\theta\zeta} \\ \tau_{s\zeta} \\ \tau_{s\theta} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} & 0 & 0 & c_{16} \\ c_{12} & c_{22} & c_{23} & 0 & 0 & c_{26} \\ c_{13} & c_{23} & c_{33} & 0 & 0 & c_{36} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{44} & c_{45} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{45} & c_{55} & 0 \\ c_{16} & c_{26} & c_{36} & 0 & 0 & c_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_s \\ \varepsilon_\theta \\ \varepsilon_\zeta \\ \gamma_{\theta\zeta} \\ \gamma_{s\zeta} \\ \gamma_{s\theta} \end{Bmatrix},$$

where $\sigma_s, \sigma_\theta, \sigma_\zeta, \tau_{s\zeta}, \tau_{\theta\zeta}, \tau_{s\theta}$ and $\varepsilon_s, \varepsilon_\theta, \varepsilon_\zeta, \gamma_{s\zeta}, \gamma_{\theta\zeta}, \gamma_{s\theta}$ are the stress and strain components, respectively. The laminated system is heterogeneous through the thickness such that the elastic constants $c_{ij} = c_{ij}(\zeta)$ are piecewisely continuous functions of ζ .

The kinematic relations in terms of the conical coordinates s, θ and ζ can be expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_s \\ \varepsilon_\theta \\ \varepsilon_\zeta \\ \gamma_{s\zeta} \\ \gamma_{\theta\zeta} \\ \gamma_{s\theta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_s & 0 & 0 \\ s_\alpha/h_\theta & \partial_\theta/h_\theta & c_\alpha/h_\theta \\ 0 & 0 & \partial_\zeta \\ \partial_\zeta & 0 & \partial_s \\ 0 & \partial_\zeta-(c_\alpha/h_\theta) & \partial_\theta/h_\theta \\ \partial_\theta/h_\theta & \partial_s-(s_\alpha/h_\theta) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_s \\ u_\theta \\ u_\zeta \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

in which $h_\theta = ss_\alpha + \zeta c_\alpha$, $s_\alpha = \sin\alpha$, $c_\alpha = \cos\alpha$; $\partial_s = \partial/\partial s$, $\partial_\theta = \partial/\partial \theta$, $\partial_\zeta = \partial/\partial \zeta$; u_s , u_θ and u_ζ are the displacement components.

The stress equilibrium equations in the absence of body forces are given by

$$h_\theta \sigma_{s,s} + s_\alpha \sigma_s - s_\alpha \sigma_\theta + \tau_{s\theta,s} + c_\alpha \tau_{s\zeta} + h_\theta \tau_{s\zeta,\zeta} = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$2s_\alpha \tau_{s\theta} + h_\theta \tau_{s\theta,s} + \sigma_{\theta,\theta} + 2c_\alpha \tau_{\theta\zeta} + h_\theta \tau_{\theta\zeta,\zeta} = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$-c_\alpha \sigma_\theta + s_\alpha \tau_{s\zeta} + h_\theta \tau_{s\zeta,s} + \tau_{\theta\zeta,\theta} + c_\alpha \sigma_\zeta + h_\theta \sigma_{\zeta,\zeta} = 0. \quad (5)$$

Let us define the dimensionless field variables as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= s/R\varepsilon, & x_2 &= \theta, & x_3 &= \zeta/h; \\ u_1 &= u_s/R\varepsilon, & u_2 &= u_\theta/R\varepsilon, & u_3 &= u_\zeta/R; \\ \sigma_1 &= \sigma_s/Q, & \sigma_2 &= \sigma_\theta/Q, & \tau_{12} &= \tau_{s\theta}/Q; \\ \tau_{13} &= \tau_{s\zeta}/Q\varepsilon, & \tau_{23} &= \tau_{\theta\zeta}/Q\varepsilon, & \sigma_3 &= \sigma_\zeta/Q\varepsilon^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6a-l)$$

in which $\varepsilon^2 = h/R$ is a small parameter, usually much less than 1. R denotes a characteristic length of the shell, and Q stands for a reference elastic modulus.

The displacements u_s , u_θ , u_ζ and transverse stresses $\tau_{s\zeta}$, $\tau_{\theta\zeta}$, σ_ζ are regarded as the primary field variables in the formulation. Thus, we expand the displacements and stresses in the form of

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \varepsilon) = f^{(0)}(x_1, x_2, x_3) + \varepsilon^2 f^{(1)}(x_1, x_2, x_3) + \varepsilon^4 f^{(2)}(x_1, x_2, x_3) + \dots, \quad (7)$$

After eliminating the in-surface stresses σ_s , σ_θ and $\tau_{s\theta}$ from Eqns 1–5, introducing Eqns 6–7 into the resulting equations and collecting coefficients of equal powers of ε , we obtain the following sets of equations at various levels.

$$\text{Order } \varepsilon^0 : \quad u_3^{(0)}{}_{,3} = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^{(0)}{}_{,3} = -\mathbf{D}u_3^{(0)}, \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_s^{(0)}{}_{,3} = -\mathbf{L}_4 \mathbf{u}^{(0)} - \mathbf{L}_5 u_3^{(0)}, \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_3^{(0)}{}_{,3} = \mathbf{L}_8 \mathbf{u}^{(0)} + \tilde{l}_{63} u_3^{(0)} - \mathbf{D}^T \sigma_s^{(0)} - \tau_{13}^{(0)} s_\alpha / r, \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_m^{(0)} = \mathbf{L}_9 \mathbf{u}^{(0)} + \mathbf{L}_{10} u_3^{(0)}, \quad (12)$$

Order ε^{2k} , ($k=1, 2, 3, \dots$)

$$u_3^{(k)}{}_{,3} = -\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u}^{(k-1)} - \tilde{l}_{33} u_3^{(k-1)} + (Q/c_{33}) \sigma_3^{(k-2)}, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^{(k)}{}_{,3} = -\mathbf{D} u_3^{(k)} + \mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{u}^{(k-1)} + \mathbf{S} \sigma_s^{(k-1)} + \mathbf{L}_3 \sigma_s^{(k-2)}, \quad (14)$$

$$\sigma_s^{(k)}{}_{,3} = -\mathbf{L}_4 \mathbf{u}^{(k)} - \mathbf{L}_5 u_3^{(k)} - \mathbf{L}_6 \sigma_s^{(k-1)} - \mathbf{L}_7 \sigma_s^{(k-1)}, \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_3^{(k)}{}_{,3} = \mathbf{L}_8 \mathbf{u}^{(k)} + \tilde{l}_{63} u_3^{(k)} - \mathbf{D}^T \sigma_s^{(k)} - \tau_{13}^{(k)} s_\alpha / r - \tilde{l}_{64} \tau_{13}^{(k-1)} - \tilde{l}_{65} \sigma_3^{(k-1)}, \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_m^{(k)} = \mathbf{L}_9 \mathbf{u}^{(k)} + \mathbf{L}_{10} u_3^{(k)} + \mathbf{L}_{11} \sigma_3^{(k-1)}, \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{u} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{Bmatrix}$, $\sigma_s = \begin{Bmatrix} \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \end{Bmatrix}$, $\sigma_m = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{13} \\ \tilde{l}_{23} \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{14} & \tilde{l}_{15} \\ \tilde{l}_{15} & \tilde{l}_{25} \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{L}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{31} & \tilde{l}_{32} \end{bmatrix}$

$$\mathbf{L}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{l}_{22} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{l}_{26} & \tilde{l}_{27} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L}_4 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{41} & \tilde{l}_{42} \\ \tilde{l}_{51} & \tilde{l}_{52} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L}_5 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{43} \\ \tilde{l}_{53} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L}_6 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{l}_{55} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{L}_7 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{46} \\ \tilde{l}_{56} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L}_8 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{61} & \tilde{l}_{62} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L}_9 = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{71} & \tilde{l}_{72} \\ \tilde{l}_{81} & \tilde{l}_{82} \\ \tilde{l}_{91} & \tilde{l}_{92} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L}_{10} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{l}_{73} \\ \tilde{l}_{83} \\ \tilde{l}_{93} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{L}_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{c}_{13} \\ \tilde{c}_{23} \\ \tilde{c}_{36} \end{bmatrix},$$

and the explicit expressions of \tilde{l}_{ij} are omitted for brevity.

The associated dimensionless boundary conditions for various orders are

Order ε^0 :

On the inner and outer surfaces the following traction conditions must be satisfied:

$$[\tau_{13}^{(0)}, \tau_{23}^{(0)}, \sigma_3^{(0)}] = [q_1^+, q_2^+, q_3^+] \quad \text{on } x_3 = 1, \quad (18)$$

$$[\tau_{13}^{(0)}, \tau_{23}^{(0)}, \sigma_3^{(0)}] = [q_1^-, q_2^-, q_3^-] \quad \text{on } x_3 = -1, \quad (19)$$

Along the edges one member of each pair of the following quantities must be satisfied:

$$n_1 \sigma_1^{(0)} + n_2 \tau_{12}^{(0)} = \bar{p}_1, \quad \text{or } u_1^{(0)} = \bar{u}_1, \quad (20)$$

$$n_1 \tau_{12}^{(0)} + n_2 \sigma_2^{(0)} = \bar{p}_2, \quad \text{or} \quad u_2^{(0)} = \bar{u}_2, \quad (21)$$

$$n_1 \sigma_{13}^{(0)} + n_2 \tau_{23}^{(0)} = \bar{p}_3, \quad \text{or} \quad u_3^{(0)} = \bar{u}_3. \quad (22)$$

Order ε^{2k} ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$):

On the inner and outer surfaces the following traction conditions must be satisfied:

$$[\tau_{13}^{(k)}, \tau_{23}^{(k)}, \sigma_3^{(k)}] = [0, 0, 0] \quad \text{on} \quad x_3 = \pm 1, \quad (23)$$

Along the edges one member of each pair of the following quantities must be satisfied:

$$n_1 \sigma_1^{(k)} + n_2 \tau_{12}^{(k)} = 0, \quad \text{or} \quad u_1^{(0)} = 0, \quad (24)$$

$$n_1 \tau_{12}^{(k)} + n_2 \sigma_2^{(k)} = 0, \quad \text{or} \quad u_2^{(k)} = 0, \quad (25)$$

$$n_1 \tau_{13}^{(k)} + n_2 \tau_{23}^{(k)} = 0, \quad \text{or} \quad u_3^{(k)} = 0, \quad (26)$$

where $q_1^\pm = q_s^\pm / Q\varepsilon$, $q_2^\pm = q^\pm / Q\varepsilon$, $q_3^\pm = q_\zeta^\pm / Q\varepsilon^2$; $\bar{p}_1 = \bar{p}_s / Q$, $\bar{p}_2 = \bar{p}_\theta / Q$, $\bar{p}_3 = \bar{p}_\zeta / Q\varepsilon$; $\bar{u}_1 = \bar{u}_s / \sqrt{Rh}$, $\bar{u}_2 = \bar{u}_\theta$ and $\bar{u}_3 = \bar{u}_\zeta / R$.

After successive integration and a simple manipulation, we obtain the basic equilibrium equations of ε^0 -order as follows:

$$K_{11} u_1^0 + K_{12} u_2^0 + K_{13} u_3^0 = q_1^+ - q_1^-, \quad (27)$$

$$K_{21} u_1^0 + K_{22} u_2^0 + K_{23} u_3^0 = q_2^+ - q_2^-, \quad (28)$$

$$K_{31} u_1^0 + K_{32} u_2^0 + K_{33} u_3^0 = (q_1^+ + q_1^-)_{,1} + s_\alpha (q_1^+ + q_1^-) / r + (q_2^+ + q_2^-)_{,2} / r + q_3^+ - q_3^-, \quad (29)$$

where K_{ij} are the corresponding differential operators.

Examining the governing equations for displacements in CST [1], we find that the CST equations are reproduced from Eqns 27–29 after imposing a geometry assumption of the circular conical shell: $\zeta / \text{stan}\alpha \ll 1$. The CST thus has been shown to be a first-order approximation to the three-dimensional theory.

After proceeding to the ε^{2k} -order, we obtain the CST type equations with nonhomogeneous terms carried over from the leading-order solution.

$$K_{11} u_1^k + K_{12} u_2^k + K_{13} u_3^k = f_{1k}(x_1, x_2, 1), \quad (30)$$

$$K_{21} u_1^k + K_{22} u_2^k + K_{23} u_3^k = f_{2k}(x_1, x_2, 1), \quad (31)$$

$$K_{31} u_1^k + K_{32} u_2^k + K_{33} u_3^k = f_{3k}(x_1, x_2, 1) + \mathbf{D}^T \mathbf{f}_k(x_1, x_2, 1) + s_\alpha f_{1k}(x_1, x_2, 1) / r. \quad (32)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{3k}(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= -\int_{-1}^{x_3} [\mathbf{D}^T \mathbf{f}_k + s_a f_{1k}/r + \mathbf{L}_8 \boldsymbol{\phi}_k + \tilde{l}_{63} \phi_{3k} - \tilde{l}_{64} \tau_{13}^{(k-1)} - \tilde{l}_{65} \sigma_3^{(k-1)}] d\eta, \\
\mathbf{f}_k &= \begin{Bmatrix} f_{1k}(x_1, x_2, x_3) \\ f_{2k}(x_1, x_2, x_3) \end{Bmatrix} = \int_{-1}^{x_3} [\mathbf{L}_4 \boldsymbol{\phi}_k + \mathbf{L}_5 \phi_{3k} + \mathbf{L}_6 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s^{(k-1)} + \mathbf{L}_7 \sigma_3^{(k-1)}] d\eta, \\
\phi_{3k}(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= -\int_0^{x_3} [\mathbf{L}_1 \mathbf{u}^{(k-1)} + \tilde{l}_{33} u_3^{(k-1)} - Q \sigma_3^{(k-2)} / c_{33}] d\eta, \\
\boldsymbol{\phi}_k &= \begin{Bmatrix} \phi_{1k}(x_1, x_2, x_3) \\ \phi_{2k}(x_1, x_2, x_3) \end{Bmatrix} = \int_0^{x_3} [\mathbf{L}_2 \mathbf{u}^{(k-1)} + \mathbf{S} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s^{(k-1)} + \mathbf{L}_3 \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s^{(k-2)} - \mathbf{D} \phi_{3k}] d\eta.
\end{aligned}$$

By observation of the equations among Eqns 27–29, 30–32, it is found that the differential operators K_{ij} for various orders remain the same and the nonhomogeneous terms for higher-order level can be calculated from the lower-order solutions. Thus, solution procedure for the leading order can be repeatedly applied for the solution to the higher-order level.

THE METHOD OF DIFFERENTIAL QUADRATURE

In the method of differential quadrature, the spatial derivative of a function at a particular grid point is approximated as a weighted linear sum of the function values at all grid points in the domain of that variable. Thus, the derivatives of $\tilde{u}_l^k(x_1)$ ($l=1,2,3$) at $x_1 = \bar{x}_i$ are expressed as

$$\tilde{u}_l^k(\bar{x}_i)_{,1} = \sum_{j=1}^N c_{ij}^{(1)} \tilde{u}_l^k(\bar{x}_j), \quad (33)$$

$$\tilde{u}_l^k(\bar{x}_i)_{,11} = \sum_{j=1}^N c_{ij}^{(2)} \tilde{u}_l^k(\bar{x}_j), \quad (34)$$

$$\tilde{u}_l^k(\bar{x}_i)_{,111} = \sum_{j=1}^N c_{ij}^{(3)} \tilde{u}_l^k(\bar{x}_j), \quad (35)$$

$$\tilde{u}_l^k(\bar{x}_i)_{,1111} = \sum_{j=1}^N c_{ij}^{(4)} \tilde{u}_l^k(\bar{x}_j), \quad (36)$$

where $l = 1, 2, 3$; $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and N is the total number of the grid points; \bar{x}_i ($i=1,2,\dots,N$) are the coordinates of the grid points.

The coordinates of the grid points along x_1 direction are chosen as

$$\bar{x}_j = R_1 / (s_\alpha \sqrt{Rh}) + \frac{1 - \cos[(j-1)\pi/(N-1)]}{2} [(R_2 - R_1) / (s_\alpha \sqrt{Rh})] \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (37)$$

The Lagrange interpolated polynomials are adopted as the set of test functions. Substituting the test functions into Eqn 33 yields

$$c_{ij}^{(1)} = \frac{M(\bar{x}_i)_{,1}}{(\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j) M(\bar{x}_j)_{,1}} \quad (i \neq j), \quad (38)$$

$$c_{ii}^{(1)} = \frac{M(\bar{x}_i)_{,11}}{2M(\bar{x}_i)_{,1}} \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (39)$$

A recurrence relation for the m th-order weighting coefficients $c_{ij}^{(m)}$ was derived by Shu and Richards [6] and was given by

$$c_{ij}^{(m)} = m \left[c_{ii}^{(m-1)} c_{ij}^{(1)} - \frac{c_{ij}^{(m-1)}}{(\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j)} \right] \quad (i \neq j), \quad (41)$$

$$c_{ii}^{(m)} = - \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j \neq i)}}^N c_{ij}^{(m)} \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (42)$$

According to Eqns 33–36, the governing equations and the corresponding boundary conditions can be expressed as the linear algebraic equations in terms of the mid-surface displacements at all of the grid points. It is noted that for a well-posed problem the number of equations should be identical to the number of unknowns. A treatment commonly used in the literature [5] is adopted in the present study. The first two governing equations, Eqns 27–28, expressed in terms of the mid-surface displacements at all of the grid points are applied at the interior points ($i = 2, 3, \dots, N-1$) and that of the third governing equation, Eqn 29, is applied at the interior points ($i = 3, 4, \dots, N-2$). By inclusion of four boundary conditions at each edge, we establish a system of $3N$ algebraic equations in $3N$ unknowns (3 mid-surface displacements at each grid point) which can be accomplished by the well-known methods. Thus, the mid-surface displacements of the leading order at the grid points can be obtained. Afterwards, the ε^0 -order solution can be determined from the relevant expressions. In view of the recurrence of the basic equations for various orders, the higher-order modifications can be determined in the hierarchic manner.

ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

Numerical results on laminated circular conical shells available for comparison purpose can hardly be found. The present solution may serve as a benchmark in assessing the applicability of various two-dimensional shell theories. In the computations the simply supported circular conical shells subjected to the sinusoidal load, $q_{\zeta}^{-} = -q_0 \sin[\pi(s - R_1/s_a)/L] \cos(4\theta)$, at the inner surface are considered. In the computations the material properties are given by $E_L/E_T = 25$, $G_{LT}/E_T = 0.5$, $G_{TT}/E_T = 0.2$. The geometry parameters are $L/R_1 = 4$, $R_1/2h = 10, 100$. The stresses and displacements are normalized as

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{\sigma}_1, \bar{\sigma}_2, \bar{\tau}_{12}) &= [10(2h)^2/q_0 R_1^2] (\sigma_s, \sigma_{\theta}, \tau_{s\theta}), \\ (\bar{\tau}_{13}, \bar{\tau}_{23}) &= [10(2h)/q_0 R_1] (\tau_{s\zeta}, \tau_{\theta\zeta}), \quad \bar{\sigma}_3 = \sigma_{\zeta}/q_0, \\ \bar{u}_3 &= 10E_L u_{\zeta} (2h)^3 / q_0 R_1^4. \end{aligned} \quad (43a-d)$$

The results of mid-surface displacements in the cases of $\alpha = \pi/6$ are shown in Table 1. The total number of grid points is taken to be 11, 13 and 15. Table 1 shows that convergence of the present asymptotic solution is fast. The convergent solutions yield at the ε^2 -order ($N=15$) in the cases of the thin shells ($R_1/2h=100$) and at the ε^4 -order ($N=15$) in the cases of the moderately thick shells ($R_1/2h=10$). It is shown that rapidly convergent interlaminar stresses are obtained.

CONCLUSIONS

An asymptotic theory is developed for the bending analysis of the laminated circular conical shells by application of the perturbation method. The asymptotic theory is based on the three-dimensional elasticity theory without making static and kinematic assumptions *a priori*. By means of the DQ method the governing differential equations and the corresponding boundary conditions for various orders can be replaced by a well-posed problem consisting of a system of algebraic equations in the mid-surface displacements at all of the grid points. Solutions of the system of algebraic equations can be obtained readily. Application of the present theory to laminated shells reveals that both the DQ method and the asymptotic solution are convergent rapidly. The convergent results yield at the ε^2 -order for the thin shells ($R_1/2h = 100$) and at the ε^4 -order for the moderately thick shells ($R_1/2h = 10$).

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Fig. 1: The geometry and coordinate system for a circular conical shell

Table 1: Displacements at the mid-surface of laminated conical shells

$$(\bar{u}_3(L/2,0,0), L/R_1=4, \alpha = \pi/6)$$

Laminates	$R_1/2h$	ε^{2k}	DQ ($N=11$)	DQ ($N=13$)	DQ ($N=15$)	CST ($N=15$)
[0/90]	10	ε^0	30.6436	30.6566	30.6605	30.7324
		ε^2	32.9798	32.9897	33.0055	
		ε^4	33.1100	33.1307	33.1392	
		ε^6	33.0843	33.0926	33.1041	
	100	ε^0	2.0065	2.0035	2.0014	2.0017
		ε^2	2.0124	2.0093	2.0072	
		ε^4	2.0121	2.0091	2.0069	
		ε^6	2.0121	2.0090	2.0069	
[0/90/0]	10	ε^0	45.8757	45.8630	45.8584	45.8547
		ε^2	48.8478	48.8473	48.8572	
		ε^4	48.8938	48.8991	48.9076	
		ε^6	48.8951	48.8979	48.9060	
	100	ε^0	1.9934	1.9907	1.9893	1.9893
		ε^2	1.9948	1.9921	1.9907	
		ε^4	1.9947	1.9920	1.9906	
		ε^6	1.9947	1.9920	1.9906	